

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

JUBEMAY A. MANGALINO

**RESILIENCE IN A TROPICAL COASTAL COMMUNITY:
THE CASE OF ANIB, SIPOCOT, CAMARINES SUR**

Special Problem Adviser:

DR. CONSUELO DL. HABITO
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

25 July 2023

Permission is given for the following people to have access to this special problem:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No

Student's Signature: _____

Signature of Special Problem Adviser: _____

Resilience in a Tropical Coastal Community:
The Case of Anib, Sipocot, Camarines Sur i

University Permission Page

RESILIENCE IN A TROPICAL COASTAL COMMUNITY: THE CASE OF ANIB, SIPOCOT, CAMARINES SUR

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to: _____

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly, and research purposes.*

JUBEMAY A. MANGALINO and JULY 25, 2023
Signature over Student Name and Date

ACCEPTANCE PAGE

This Special Problem titled: **“RESILIENCE IN A TROPICAL COASTAL COMMUNITY: THE CASE OF ANIB, SIPOCOT, CAMARINES SUR”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management (MENRM).

Consuelo D. Habito

CONSUELO DL. HABITO, PhD
Faculty-in-charge, ENRM 290 (Special Problem)

30 July 2023
(Date)

Consuelo D. Habito

CONSUELO DL. HABITO, PhD
Program Chair

30 July 2023
(Date)

Joane V. Serrano

JOANE V. SERRANO, Ph.D.
Dean
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

25 September 2023
Date

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards MENRM.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25, 000 words in length, exclusive of tables, annexes and appendices.

JUBEMAY A. MANGALINO

Acknowledgment

I would like to acknowledge the following, who in one way or another helped in the completion of this study.

To my family, Pat and our cats, for inspiring me to push through my graduate studies.

To the Local Government Unit of Sipocot, particularly the Municipal Agriculture Office, for the assistance in identifying and coordinating with the target study areas, and the Anib Barangay Council for the support provided during data collection stage.

To my professors at UPOU FMDS for the fruitful discussions on my elective and major subjects. Special mention goes to Dr. Connie Habito, for patiently guiding me in this study.

To my fellow Bicolanos who, despite the constant test of various calamities, have proven how to be adaptive and resilient.

And above all to the Almighty, for giving me the wisdom, strength and guidance every day.

To everyone, I offer this to you.

-Jube

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Declaration	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Table of Contents	vi
List of Figures	vii
ABSTRACT	viii
I. INTRODUCTION	1
II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE	2
III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY	6
IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY	7
V. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA	8
VI. METHODOLOGY	10
VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	11
VIII. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION	16
IX. REFERENCES	19

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1	Framework of Resilience at Different Levels	5
Figure 2	Municipality Map of Sipocot, Camarines Sur	9
Figure 3	Sex Disaggregation of FGD Participants	11
Figure 4	Age Bracket of the FGD Participants	11
Figure 5	Primary Occupation of the FGD Participants	12
Figure 6	Other Sources of Income of FGD Participants	12

ABSTRACT

Resilience has been a common terminology constantly used side by side with disaster. However, it is more than that. It can be displayed on a day-to-day living especially on vulnerable areas such as remote communities.

This study highlights the concept of resilience as perceived by a coastal community in Sipocot, Camarines Sur. The study was conducted through a focus group discussion participated by representatives of youth, women, men, and the barangay local government unit. Their collective responses can be summarized into four important aspects of resilience. These are: (1) the concept of resilience is manifested in the daily lives of local communities, not only during disasters; (2) survival is the primary concern when we talk about resilience and this is manifested by economic stability; (3) policies and its enforcement are vital to resilience building; and (4) various community issues are interrelated, therefore solutions must be holistic.

Keywords: Resilience, Community Resilience, Social and Ecological Resilience

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding resilience is critical to appropriately adapt, manage and address various threats that are being encountered by the communities. For the past years, the concept of resilience building has been commonly used, especially in the areas of disaster risk management and climate change where it has already become an indispensable topic in both development and humanitarian aspects (Clark-Ginsberg, 2020).

Various literatures showed how the concept of resilience is defined and reflected in different cases and fields. While there are various definitions of resilience, it generally reflects the ability of the system to adapt and function despite the shocks and stresses that it encounters.

In building community resilience, duty bearers normally follow a set of initiatives that are cascaded from the national governing bodies. These initiatives are being implemented in various areas particularly those considered as highly vulnerable. However, these initiatives are often not tailor-fitted to the needs and reality on the ground. Further, the lack of insights and initiatives from duty bearers to modify these initiatives based on local needs sometimes results in failure generally due to lack of appreciation and ownership of the community beneficiaries.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Over the years, the concept of resilience has been widely studied and discussed in various fields. As emphasized by Thoren (2014), the concept of resilience has evolved through time and cuts across different discipline to include psychology, sociology, ecology as well as disaster management.

In 1973, the concept was popularized by C.S. Holling in the field of ecological systems. In his paper “Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems,” he argued that traditional ecological theories put emphasis on the equilibrium and stability of ecosystem, and neglecting the ecosystems' innate ability to alter, adapt, and survive in case of disruptions. In his adaptive cycle model, he emphasized that ecosystems go through different phases of growth, conservation, release, and reorganization. The occurrence of disturbances although can disrupt the stability of an ecosystem which can lead to a phase of release and reorganization, can sometimes provide opportunities for renewal, which may lead back to the growth phase once again.

In the field of Psychology, several research studies were conducted related to resilience. Among those is Ann Masten, an American Psychologist who authored the paper entitled “Resilience in Developmental Systems” which tried to put resilience in the context of developmental systems - dynamic and full of interaction. She argued that resilience at an individual level is not solely attributed to the individual's own trait/capacity, but is shaped and greatly influenced by his/ her interaction with the environment through positive, supportive, and nurturing relationship. It underscores that the interrelationship between individuals and their environments is vital in resilience development.

Relatedly, Adger (2000) examined the relationship between social resilience and ecological resilience emphasizing the interconnection between human and natural systems. He emphasized that both the social and ecological resilience share the same underlying principles and dynamics with its ability to adapt and persist in case of disturbances. Considering its interconnectedness, the changes in social system can affect ecological resilience, and vice versa. Thus, integrated strategies are necessary to address environmental changes taking into consideration the interrelationship of social and ecological systems, and that actions in one domain can have significant consequences on the other.

Other than abovementioned discipline, the concept of resilience is popularly known these days in the realm of climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction (Keating, 2020). In the context of disaster risk, resilience is defined as the ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate, adapt to, transform and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner, including the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions through risk management (UNDRR, 2017). As emphasized

by Ganji (2019), community resilience is complicated and multi-dimensional. It has become an integrative approach to address issues related to stress, shocks, social protection, food security, and disasters (Busayo et. al, 2020). It involves the collective capacity of individuals, organizations, and institutions to adapt and thrive in the face of adversity.

Many scholars emphasized the interconnectedness between social, economic, and environmental factors in shaping resilience. For instance, Norris et al. (2008) proposed the Community Resilience Framework, which highlights four core elements: community resources, social networks, communication and information, and leadership and governance. These components work together and are essential for promoting community resilience. Community resources supply the required assets while social networks encourage collaboration and mutual support. Strong leadership and governance enable coordinated responses, while effective communication and information flow enable informed decision-making.

Furthermore, social capital, community engagement, and infrastructure have significant impact on community resilience. Aldrich and Meyer (2015) emphasized the role of social capital and networks in fostering cooperation and collective action. According to Cutter et al. (2008), infrastructure is essential for minimizing disruptions and facilitating swift recovery.

Building community resilience requires a holistic understanding and approach to these concerns. Policy makers and practitioners in the field of community resilience can develop comprehensive strategies that can improve communities' ability for adaptation and foster long term resilience by acknowledging the interrelationship of social capital, community engagement, and infrastructure.

Coastal communities are exposed to various stressors and shocks. Different studies showed that coastal communities particularly fisherfolks are considered to be among the poorest and as one of the most vulnerable sectors. Sea level rise, increasing frequency and magnitude of tropical cyclones, flooding, erosion, pollution and coastal encroachment are among the various issues that threaten these communities (Busayo et.al., 2020).

Increasing community resilience is necessary to ensure that the population is able to bounce back in times of shocks and stress. Thus, responsive and efficient actions need to be put in place as part of response and recovery interventions to the specific shocks. Typically, in the absence of clear understanding of resilience, external organizations lack explicit guidelines or strategies on how to increase community resilience or to measure the effectiveness of their efforts (Patin, 2020). This is when the efficiency and success of interventions becomes problematic as local perspective is neglected and set aside.

Conceptual Framework

Presented in Figure 1 is the conceptual framework of the study which highlights the different levels of resilience and the interconnectedness of each level. It is guided by the systems thinking of human ecological framework which explains the interaction between human and the environment, as was also argued by various studies including Adger (2000) and Masten (2001).

The framework emphasizes the following points:

First, the concept of resilience is applicable at different system starting from smaller unit to larger unit of the society, in this case from individual, to family, community or groups of communities. The occurrence of a disruption or stressors, and the ability of that system to respond and cope with changes brought by the stressors are important factors to test resilience.

Second, each system is affected by different stressors or disturbances at different degree. Similarly, coping and response mechanisms from these stressors also vary in each system depending on various factors including its respective capacities and existing vulnerabilities.

Third, resilience of each system is not built in silos. The interaction between these systems creates a level of resilience wherein the higher level of resilience is greatly influenced by the status of lower-level resilience. Community resilience will be difficult to attain if the primary stressors of those in the lower levels are not properly addressed. This is encapsulated in the popular slogan “Leaving No One Behind” as adopted by United Nations.

Fourth, considering the interrelationship of each system, there is a need for integrated approaches to address social-ecological challenges.

Figure 1. Framework of Resilience at Different Levels

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, the study aims to determine the perception of coastal communities on resilience. Specifically, it aims to:

1. Determine the stressors, environmental changes and societal issues that prevents or hinders the community members to attain productivity;
2. Identify the initiatives or strategies being adopted by the community to overcome these stressors or environmental changes;
3. Recommend possible policies and appropriate initiatives which can be adopted by the duty bearers relative to resilience building

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to explore how coastal communities perceive resilience based on their own experiences. Results will contribute in bridging the information gap to better understand the concept of resilience which eventually can be used as basis for the duty bearers in determining appropriate interventions to strengthen the resilience of these communities.

V. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The municipality of Sipocot is one of the 114 municipalities of the Bicol region, the fifth administrative region in the country. It is located in north-eastern part under the province of Camarines Sur, with a total land area of 24, 129 hectares comprising of 46 barangays.

Barangay Anib, one of the barangays in the municipality of Sipocot is a coastal community facing San Miguel Bay. It is approximately 8.50 kilometers northeast of the Sipocot Poblacion. Its total land area is around 446 hectares which is generally of undulating to rolling. Around 97 percent of the total land area of the barangay is considered agricultural. Most of the community members rely on fishing as a source of income, while others are into farming (LGU Sipocot, 2015).

The community heavily relies on the abundant resources available in the San Miguel Bay which is considered as one of the major fishing ground in the Bicol region. Among the marine organisms that can be found in the Bay include various species of rays, sharks, sardines, anchovies, eels, among others. The Abo (*Otolithes ruber*) is considered as the most common demersal fish in the area (Pauly, et.al, 1982).

Figure 2. Municipality Map of Sipocot, Camarines Sur

VI. METHODOLOGY

A qualitative research design was adopted for the study. To gather the data needed, four sets of focus group discussions (FGD) were conducted which participated by individuals representing the following sector: (a) women; (b) men; (c) youth; and (d) barangay officials. Prior to the FGD, initial coordination with the municipal and barangay local government units were conducted. Demographic profiles containing basic information of the participants were gathered.

To facilitate discussion, a set of common guide questions were utilized. In determining the community's perception on resilience, participants were asked about the stressors, environmental changes and/or societal issues encountered by the community which affected, hindered and prevented them from being productive. The responses were categorized into four thematic areas, to wit: (a) physical; (b) socio-cultural; (c) economic; (d) policy and governance; and (e) natural system. Similar strategy was adopted to determine their adaptive practices to address and deal with the identified stressors, environmental changes and societal issues.

During the FGD, questions were delivered in Filipino and the local dialect (*Bicolano*) to ensure better understanding and encourage a participative discussion. Presented in Annex A are the demographic profile for participants' basic information, and initial FGD guide questions.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographics

A total of 32 community members participated on the focus group discussion representing the four major sector, to wit: women, men, youth and barangay local government unit officials. Of these, around 28 percent ages 56-65 years old, while 25 percent ages 16-25 years old. Figures 1 and 2 show the sex disaggregation and age bracket of the FGD participants.

Figure 3. Sex Disaggregation of the FGD Participants

Figure 4. Age Bracket of the FGD Participants

Comparing the primary source of income of the respondents, 41 percent are government employees, mostly as members of the barangay local government unit. Meanwhile, 16 percent are farmers and fisherfolks. Among the respondents who are government employee, 62 percent are also into farming and fishing as their secondary source of income. Figure 3 and 4 show the primary and secondary sources of income of the respondents.

Figure 5. Primary Occupation of the FGD Participants

Figure 6. Other Sources of Income of the FGD Participants

Stressors, Shocks and Issues

Results of the focused group discussion showed that the community's primary issue revolves around economic-related stressors which include low income or revenue, and lack of economic opportunities in the locality. Being a coastal community, the low income is attributed to dwindling fish catch as a result of decades-long issues of illegal fishing such as proliferation of trawls, and other fishing malpractices. This issue is further aggravated by year-round calamities including tropical cyclones which constantly damages the communities' fishing boats and gears. In addition, the effect of the southwest monsoon season "Habagat" which happens from May to October further prevents fishermen from going into fishing due to big waves and strong winds.

The farmers in the community are not excluded from the abovementioned economic-related stressors. Various factors such as underutilization of land due to lack of water source and unfertile soils, small farm size, high cost of inputs, and lack of infrastructure support (e.g farm-to-market roads) results in low agricultural productivity. These difficulties of the farmers are further exacerbated by low selling price of their agri-produce, the lack of market linkage support, and losses due to calamities.

To make ends meet, the community relies on other means to feed and support their families. One such means is lending which further pushes the community members at the brink of poverty. The high interest rate imposed by these enterprises coupled by the inability to pay on time exposes the community members to the risk of falling more deeply in debt.

Other issues that were commonly identified were environmental-related stressors. First is the improper disposal of unsegregated wastes, and the absence of a common waste disposal facility in the community. Despite the regular coastal clean-up and barangay policy on anti-littering, the issue on solid wastes is among the concerns that stresses the community especially that it aggravates issues on pollution, flooding, and spreading of common preventable diseases.

Another issue which was commonly identified by the participants is related to disaster and climate change, particularly the occurrence of extreme weather events such as tropical cyclones, and erosion or loss of coastal land. It was observed that over the years, the occurrence of the natural calamities have increased in terms of frequency and intensity. Further, the continuous erosion or loss of coastal land being experienced by the people through time also adds to these stressors. As shared during the discussion, an approximately 400 sq. meter of land in the school site is already submerged in water.

The effects and impact of these issues particularly the damages it brings to the livelihood and properties further lowers the quality of the living condition of the people in Anib.

The lack of capacity of parents to send their children to school particularly in higher education was also identified as a community issue. In some cases, due to poverty, once the child is old enough to assist their parents, whether in the farm fields or in household chores, they are obliged to help. For most families, bringing food to the table is a priority while education (i.e earning a college degree) is relegated as a lesser priority or even a privilege.

The sudden shift of the learning method from the face-to-face teaching manner to a modular/ distance learning method during the pandemic also affected the quality of education as observed by the community members. Difficulties in understanding the lessons, additional expense for the modules and gadgets including internet load, and the poor telecommunication internet service are among the struggles faced by the students and parents in this modular/distance method. However, participants highlighted a positive side of modular/distance learning. College students consider the method cheaper as they don't have to pay for transportation and dormitory expenses as compared to when they are having the face to face class.

Comparing the responses among the groups, it is important to note that the youth sector put more weight on the issue of education. On the other hand, participants for both men and women sectors, who are mostly parents, emphasized on the economic aspect, particularly on the lack of livelihood opportunities which limit their income and the way they support their families.

Adaptive Strategies

To overcome the above mentioned stressors, various strategies are being adopted by the community members. On the economic aspect, community members find other sources of income or employ multiple jobs to make ends meet and continuously support their families. For example, instead of just relying on fishing and the sea, fisher folks are also resorting to farming, construction works, and other blue-collar jobs especially during Habagat season when there is minimal to no fish catch at all. Some are also venturing to neighboring communities or towns to look for other jobs. The village or barangay ordinance prohibiting community members to engage in illegal means of earning income such as gambling particularly cock fighting (*tupada*) is one of the policy imposed by the local officials to address financial problems of the people.

To address issues on solid waste, regular coastal clean-up is being conducted. The village also issued a barangay ordinance penalizing offenders. Waste segregation is also being practiced in some households to ensure lesser plastics and non-biodegradable wastes, while some bury their waste in their respective area.

Construction of seawall and breakwater were also adopted to address the effects of storm surge and sea level rise. Some households have relocated their settlements to higher grounds. Households situated in danger zones are also enforced to observe pre-emptive evacuation, especially if there are storm warning signals raised. Community preparedness activities are also being undertaken such as capacity building, drills and establishment of community-based early warning systems.

To continuously support the education needs, some of the students are working part-time to earn. Hiring of tutors or paying somebody to answer the modules are also being adopted just to make sure that the assigned tasks to students are accomplished. This practice however further compromises the quality of education of children as observed by the participants.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Recommendations

Given the chance to provide solutions to address the various stressors, issues and shocks that the community members are experiencing, participants recommended the following:

1. Economic Aspect

Provision of subsidies is the commonly identified solution by the community members. This can be in the form of financial subsidies or input/material subsidies such as seeds and fertilizers for farmers, and fishing gears, motorized boats and fuel for fisherfolks. Providing opportunities for alternative modes of income was also identified particularly in starting up small businesses such as backyard piggery/ poultry, food-related business, and convenience stores. Further, linking agri-fishery products to larger markets was also identified as a vital strategy to guarantee income of both the farmers and the fisherfolks. To sustain these initiatives, it was recommended that commitment of the target beneficiaries must be ensured and capacity building activities must be conducted prior to the release of any support.

Strict and unbiased enforcement of fishery policies was also recommended particularly to address the issue of illegal fishing. As emphasized, the capacity and police power of community members to fight trawl operators is very limited making them on the disadvantage side, thus stronger force from higher authorities is needed. Meanwhile, to address the problem of lending, the recommendations are enactment of policy that will regulate the proliferation of lending enterprises, and establishing an interest rate quota to prevent exploitation of the community members who are dependent on these enterprises.

2. Social Aspect (i.e Education)

Returning to face-to-face mode of classes is the identified solution to address the issue of declining quality of education in the community. Providing scholarships or educational assistance to deserving students was also determined as another solution. However, the selection process must be properly carried out and disseminated to the community members following particular criteria such as lack of financial capacity of the family and the student's willingness to study.

3. Environmental Aspect.

With regards to the issue of solid waste, community members acknowledge that a comprehensive, multi-sectoral and holistic approach needs to be established. Individual responsibility was also determined as an important factor to address the issue. Case in point, the segregation at source and discipline of the people in managing the household wastes is vital to ensure the cleanliness of the surrounding. In addition to the regular clean up drive and collection of waste in the barangay, enforcement of local policy is a very critical solution identified by the participants. Coordination and joint efforts of the nearby communities and local government units are also critical.

To address the issues of fisherfolks on low fish catch, providing capacity building to the Bantay Dagat members was determined as a solution. Further, providing additional incentives or honorarium, training, and equipment are also needed for them to perform their functions efficiently. Enforcement of policy declaring a close fishing season or marine protected area, if necessary, was also identified to let the ecosystem regenerate.

Conclusion

Results of the study showed that the concept of resilience is applicable at different system, starting from individual, family and the community. Despite the different applicability, among the common factors that affect resilience are (a) presence of disruption or stressors; and (b) the capacity of that system to adapt and cope with the changes caused by the certain stressors. It further highlights four important aspects relative to resilience, to wit:

First, the concept of resilience is manifested in the daily lives of local communities, in this case a coastal community. This is in contrast to the popular idea that community resilience can be seen only in times of disasters or an outbreak. This is evident in how the community members struggle on a day-to-day basis despite the various stressors and shocks yet they are able to bounce back and survive the difficulties.

Second, survival is the primary concern when we talk about resilience and this is manifested by economic stability. The discussions conducted during the study highlighted that a stable source of income is very critical for a family as this will ensure their survival. Having the capacity to afford basic necessities particularly food items is a major determinant in the quality of living of the community members. Thus, building the economic capacity of the community, particularly providing livelihood opportunities is critical for them to make ends meet and eventually ensure achievement of their full potential.

Third, policies and its enforcement are vital to resilience building. It is therefore imperative that local and national policies must be designed or tailor fitted to the needs of these local communities, bearing in mind that communities have different issues, needs, and coping mechanisms, and resilience levels.

And lastly, this study showed that various community issues are interrelated, therefore solutions must be holistic. In determining solutions, all aspects must be considered and viewed as interconnected, and not as a single aspect requiring a single solution to not further create issues arising from non-systematic approach.

REFERENCES

- Aldrich, P.D. and Meyer, M. (2014) Social Capital and Community Resilience. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 59, 254-269. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764214550299>.
- Adger, W. N. (2000). Social and ecological resilience: Are they related? *Progress in human geography*, 24(3), 347-364.
- Busayo, E.T. and Kalumba, A. M. (2020). Coastal Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Reduction: A Review of Policy, Programme and Practice for Sustainable Planning Outcomes. *Sustainability*, 12, 6450; doi:10.3390/su12166450.
- Cutter, S., Barnes, L., Berry, M., Burton, C., Evans, E., Tate, E. and Webb, J. (2008) A Place-Based Model for Understanding Community Resilience to Natural Disasters. *Global Environmental Change*, 18, 598-606. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2008.07.013>.
- Clark-Ginsberg, A., McCaul, B., Bremaud, I., Cáceres, G., Mpanje, D., Patel, S., Patel, R. (2020). Practitioner approaches to measuring community resilience: The analysis of the resilience of communities to disasters toolkit, *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, Volume 50. 101714, ISSN 2212-4209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101714>.
- Holling, C.S. (1973). Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems, (*Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*) 4: 1-23. Retrieved from https://www.zoology.ubc.ca/bdg/pdfs_bdg/2013/Holling%201973.pdf.
- Keating, A. and Hanger-Kopp, S. (2020). Practitioner perspectives of disaster resilience in international development, *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, Volume 42, 101355, ISSN 2212-4209, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101355>.
- Local Government Unit of Sipocot. Barangay Anib Socioeconomic Profile and Development Plan. 2015.
- Masten, A. S. (2001). *Ordinary magic: Resilience in development*. The Guilford Press.

- Norris, F. H., Stevens, S. P., Pfefferbaum, B., Wyche, K. F., & Pfefferbaum, R. L. (2008). Community resilience as a metaphor, theory, set of capacities, and strategy for disaster readiness. *American journal of community psychology*, 41(1-2), 127–150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10464-007-9156-6>.
- Patin, Beth (2020). What is essential?: Understanding community resilience and public libraries in the United States during disasters. DOI: 10.1002/pr2.269.
- Pauly, D. and A.N. (1982). Smallscale fisheries of San Miguel Bay, Philippines: biology and stock assessment. ICLARM Technical Reports 7. Retrieved from <http://pubs.iclarm.net/libinfo/Pdf/Pub%20TR4%207.pdf>.
- Henrik Thorén (2014). Resilience as a Unifying Concept, *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 28:3, 303-324, DOI: 10.1080/02698595.2014.953343.
- United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction. UNISDR Terminology for Disaster Risk Reduction. 2009.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A. PARTICIPANT PROFILE FORM

PROFILE

Para sa respondent o taga-sagot:

Ang survey na ito ay ginawa upang suriin ang alamin ang pang-unawa at interpretasyon ng mga miyembro ng komunidad sa usapin ng “*Resilience*”. Anumang impormasyon na iyong ilalahad sa survey na ito ay mananatiling *confidential* o *gagamitin lamang sa isang pag-aaral*.

Maraming Salamat po sa iyong pagtugon at pakikipagtulungan!

Profile ng mga kabahagi sa Focus Group Discussion

Name/*Pangalan*:

Age/*Edad*: _____ Sex/*Kasarian*:

Marital Status: _____

Highest educational attainment/ *Antas ng pinag-aralan (lagyan ng X)*

_____ College graduate

_____ College undergrad

_____ Vocational

_____ High School Graduate

_____ High School undergraduate

_____ Elementary graduate

_____ Elementary undergraduate

Iba pa (tukuyin) :

Occupation/ *Trabaho*: _____

Other sources of income other than above identified occupation/ *Iba pang pinagkakakitaan maliban sa naunang sagot*: _____

Are you the breadwinner/ *Ikaw ba ang tagapagtaguyod ng pamilya?*

Yes (Oo) _____

No (Hindi): _____

Number of dependents: _____

-end-

APPENDIX B. FGD GUIDE QUESTIONNAIRE

FGD Guide Question:

1. Determining stressors:

- What are the major causes of stressors in the community?
- What are the environmental changes and societal issues that prevents or hinders the community members to attain productivity?
- How often do you experience these issues?
- If you are to rank these issues/ stressors, what are the top three most concerns of the community? (through consensus building)

2. Adaptive Strategies

- How do the community members cope or adapt to these stressors/ issues? What are the strategies to cope with these stressors?
- What do you think should be done to address these stressors/ issues or environmental changes?

3. Others

- Are there any gaps on the assistance being provided by duty bearers to assist the communities to address the issues? If yes, what are these gaps?
- Given the answers during the discussion, if you are an outsider, how will you respond or help the community members in addressing the difficulties/ stressors that occur?
- Who should do what?

Note to Facilitator:

- Start the FGD with the rationale of the activity, and introduction of facilitators and participants
- Ensure recording of the discussion
- Translate questions in Bicol or Tagalog for better understanding

APPENDIX C. PHOTO DOCUMENTATION

Resilience in a Tropical Coastal Community:
The Case of Anib, Sipocot, Camarines Sur 25